

ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT FOR TEACHING SCIENTIFIC STYLE TO STUDENTS

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Annotation. *This study analyzes the educational and methodological support for teaching scientific style to students in higher education institutions. The research examines regulatory and legal frameworks, curricula, teaching materials, pedagogical methods, assessment systems, and digital learning resources used in the process of developing students' scientific thinking and academic writing skills. The analysis reveals several shortcomings, including the predominance of theoretical material, insufficient systematization of practical exercises, limited student-centered approaches, inadequate focus on modern academic text genres, and unclear assessment criteria. The study also explores the relationship between scientific style and academic writing, emphasizing that scientific style serves as a fundamental component of academic writing practice. The findings highlight the need to develop integrated, competency-based educational and methodological support aimed at improving students' scientific writing and analytical skills.*

Keywords: *Scientific style, academic writing, educational and methodological support, higher education, stylistics, scientific text, teaching methods, competency-based approach, scientific communication, linguistic features.*

Educational and methodological support includes the regulatory and legal framework (State Educational Standards, curriculum, course syllabus, ministerial orders and regulations); curriculum and planning (course goals and objectives, expected learning outcomes, topic plan, ratio of theoretical and practical classes); educational and methodological materials (textbooks, study guides, methodological manuals, lecture texts, practical and seminar lesson plans); teaching methods and technologies (traditional and interactive methods, modern pedagogical technologies, digital learning tools such as platforms and applications); control and assessment (current, intermediate, and final assessment forms); organization of independent learning; information-resource provision and material-technical support.

In the modern higher education system, developing students' ability to think and write in a scientific style is considered one of the important pedagogical tasks. The effectiveness of teaching scientific style largely depends on the quality and systematic organization of the educational and methodological support developed in this field. Therefore, analyzing existing educational and methodological resources that serve to teach scientific style to students is of

great relevance.

Currently, teaching scientific style in higher education institutions is mainly carried out within the framework of subjects such as Uzbek language for specific purposes, practical stylistics of the Uzbek language, fundamentals of stylistics, Uzbek language and speech culture, academic writing, and research methodology. Textbooks, teaching manuals, methodological recommendations, and electronic resources developed for these subjects cover theoretical foundations of scientific style, its lexical, grammatical, and syntactic features, as well as concepts related to scientific activity. However, analysis shows that these sources do not sufficiently systematize exercises and assignments aimed at practical mastery of scientific style.

During the analysis of textbooks related to the above-mentioned subjects, several shortcomings were identified. First, the content of lessons often contains an excessive amount of theoretical material. Although concepts related to scientific style are presented consistently, most of them are explained in continuous textual form. This makes it difficult for students to absorb information and results in lessons becoming predominantly lecture-based.

Second, the lack of methodological systematization of practical exercises reduces lesson effectiveness. Exercises are not arranged according to levels of complexity, and their objectives and expected outcomes are not clearly specified. As a result, they do not fully contribute to the consistent development of students' scientific style skills.

Third, a student-centered approach is insufficiently reflected in lessons. Forms of individual, pair, and group work are not sufficiently included, and assignments that encourage independent and creative thinking among students are limited.

Fourth, work with modern genres of scientific texts is inadequately implemented. Exercises aimed at analyzing and creating real academic writing samples such as scientific articles, annotations, theses, and reviews are rarely encountered.

Fifth, the absence of clearly defined assessment criteria is observed. The criteria for evaluating the results of practical exercises and independent work are not specified, which limits students' ability to assess their own knowledge and skills.

Although existing educational and methodological resources provide general information about types of scientific texts (annotation, thesis, article, abstract, dissertation sections), the technology of writing them, stylistic requirements, and step-by-step teaching mechanisms are often superficially explained. As a result, students face difficulties in correctly using terminology, maintaining logical coherence, and ensuring objectivity and evidence-based reasoning when creating scientific texts. Furthermore, in some methodological sources, although the analysis of linguistic units of scientific style is theoretically well developed, insufficient attention is paid to applying them in real scientific communication. Methodological guidelines designed for practical classes rarely include tasks requiring individual and creative approaches, which hinders the development of students' independent scientific thinking skills.

The potential of electronic educational and methodological resources and digital

platforms has not yet been fully utilized. The lack of interactive exercises, analysis of model scientific texts, and automated editing and assessment tools reduces the effectiveness of teaching scientific style. Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that although existing educational and methodological support for teaching scientific style is rich in content, there is a need to improve, systematize, and orient it toward practical application. Therefore, developing new integrated educational and methodological support based on a competency-based approach is one of the urgent tasks today.

Additionally, the list of literature used in the curriculum developed for the module includes the following:

Main Literature

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. From National Revival to National Progress. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2020.
2. H. Dusmatov, Z. Mahmudova. Fundamentals of Stylistics (textbook). Fergana: Classik, 2022.
3. H. Dusmatov, Z. Mahmudova. Fundamentals of Stylistics (study guide). Fergana: Classik, 2022.
4. H. Dusmatov. The Art of Words. Multi-volume monograph. Volumes 1–2. Fergana: Classik, 2024.

Additional Literature

1. H. Dusmatov. The Art of Words. Multi-volume monograph. Volumes 1–3. Fergana: Classik, 2024.
2. A. Mamajonov, M. Abdupattoyev. Text Linguistics. Textbook. Fergana: Classik, 2022.
3. M. Abdupattoyev. Poetic Syntax of the Uzbek Language. Fergana: Classik, 2021 (Appendix 1).

These sources do not fully reveal the discipline of stylistics. There are internationally recognized works in stylistics, and scientific publications by national scholars also form the conceptual foundation of this field. Issues within stylistics have been studied in world linguistics by scholars such as T.B. William, P. Demon, J.V. Cunningham, D. Crystal, D. Davy, and V.T. George; in Russian linguistics by V.V. Vinogradov, G.O. Vinokur, L.V. Shcherba, A.I. Efimov, I.R. Galperin, A.N. Gvozdev, Yu.S. Stepanov, R.A. Budagov, R.R. Geldart, and M.N. Kojina; and in Uzbek linguistics by I. Qo‘chqorto‘ev, A. Shomaqsudov, I. Rasulov, R. Qo‘ng‘urov, H. Rustamov, A. Mamajonov, I. Toshaliyev, and S. Karimov. These studies emphasize that stylistics is an independent branch of linguistics with its own object and subject of study, and they seek solutions to stylistic problems. Furthermore, several shortcomings exist in higher education subjects aimed at developing students’ scientific reading and writing skills, particularly in the academic writing course, including issues related to topics and recommended

literature.

Stephen Bailey's book *Academic Writing* is designed to improve scientific writing skills in English among students whose native language is not English. It systematically explains the process of creating scientific texts, including writing processes, key elements of text, language issues, academic vocabulary, and writing samples. This structure helps prepare students for scientific writing by integrating theoretical knowledge with practical skills. Such works are necessary not only for non-native speakers but also for researchers whose first language is English. In particular, researchers conducting scientific work in Uzbek also need such knowledge. Academic Writing is taught as a module in higher education institutions; however, despite the existence of textbooks or study guides, comprehensive monographic research has not yet been conducted. This course covers topics related to research methodology, scientific style, and scientific texts.

Academic writing aims to be clear, semi-formal, impersonal, and objective. This does not mean that pronouns such as "I" or "we" are never used, but the primary focus is on presenting information as clearly and accurately as possible. In this respect, academic writing differs from everyday speech and writing, which tend to be more personal and expressive. At first glance, this resembles the emphasis on linguistic and extralinguistic features of scientific style within linguistics. Scientific style has been studied monographically in Uzbek linguistics, including general information about stylistics, its object and functional stylistics, classification of functional styles, and linguistic and extralinguistic features of scientific style. The lexical-semantic, morphological, and syntactic characteristics of scientific style have also been described. The use of literary language units in scientific style and the distinctive features of scientific style compared to other functional styles have been studied. Scientific style is a linguistic concept that refers to language features characteristic of scientific texts.

Academic writing is the practice and methodology of writing, that is, a set of rules about how to write in a scientific environment. Academic writing can be defined as the ability to express and justify one's ideas using concise and reliable scientific text. From this perspective, scientific style is a component of academic writing, and in some cases, the concept of academic writing encompasses scientific style, because academic writing is carried out in scientific style. It cannot be imagined in conversational or literary styles. Academic writing demonstrates scientific style as its structural component, since the linguistic features of scientific work play a crucial role in practice.

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